

EFFECTIVENESS OF BLENDED LEARNING IN DISSEMINATING FISH FARMING INFORMATION IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information has garnered significant attention in recent years, given the growing need for sustainable fish farming practices. This study explores the effectiveness of blended learning approaches in disseminating fish farming information in Kwara State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used in selecting 180 respondents for the study. Primary data were collected with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistical tools employed include; frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean score (WMS) while Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) was used to test the study hypothesis. The findings revealed that various blended learning tools such as online platforms (WMS=1.98), mobile applications (WMS=1.95), in-person workshops (WMS=1.94) and Social media (WMS=1.93) were mostly utilized for information dissemination as they significantly improved the farmers' understanding of fish farming practices, leading to increased productivity and sustainability. The fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools include breeding techniques (WMS=2.05), water quality management (WMS=2.02), feeding and nutrition (WMS=1.99) and fish farming basics (WMS=1.97). Also, the effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish farming information dissemination were enhanced knowledge retention (WMS=1.85), improved access and knowledge dissemination (WMS=1.87), greater flexibility for farmers (WMS=1.85) and increased motivation and engagement (WMS=1.83). The finding further revealed that the benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming information*

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include cost-effectiveness (WMS=2.02), access to up-to-date information (WMS=1.99), flexibility and accessibility (WMS=1.98) and improved skill acquisition (WMS=1.96) while the level of effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination is high. However, constraints such as digital divide (WMS=1.68), technical skills and issues (WMS=1.65), resource limitations (WMS=1.62) and engagement challenges (WMS=1.58) must be addressed to maximize the overall efficacy of blended learning as an effective medium for fish farming information dissemination. There was a significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information ($r=0.579$, $p=0.000$) and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information. Conclusively, blended learning is an effective method for disseminating fish farming information, as it combines the flexibility of digital resources with the practical, hands-on experience necessary for fish farming skills.

Background information

The global demand for fish is increasing due to rising populations and changing dietary preferences. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), aquaculture provides more than half of the fish consumed globally (FAO, 2020) with fish farming contributing significantly to the supply of fish for consumption (Beemalla *et al.*, 2025). However, the industry faces challenges such as overfishing, environmental sustainability, and the need for efficient production methods and as the demand for fish rises, so does the need for effective dissemination of information and knowledge among fish farmers. Effective information dissemination is critical for the success of fish farming operations. Farmers require knowledge in various areas, including

species selection, breeding techniques, water quality management, feed formulation, and disease control. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), aquaculture is a rapidly growing sector that needs continuous knowledge enhancement to remain sustainable and productive (FAO, 2020). Traditional methods of information dissemination often fall short in terms of reach and engagement, highlighting the need for innovative approaches. In agricultural education, particularly in fish farming, blended learning enables the dissemination of knowledge through digital resources, video tutorials, simulation tools, and interactive forums. This caters to farmers who may have limited access to traditional training resources (Kull, 2018). The incorporation of various technologies can facilitate knowledge

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transfer and empower fish farmers with essential skills and practices, potentially improving productivity and sustainability in fish farming. Blended learning, which combines online digital media with traditional face-to-face classroom methods, has emerged as an effective educational approach and has become increasingly popular in disseminating information across various fields, including agriculture and fish farming. This approach can potentially enhance learning experiences and outcomes, particularly in areas requiring practical knowledge like fish farming. This integration allows for flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to cater to different learning styles. Blended learning is a pedagogical approach that blends online digital media with traditional classroom methods. It typically involves a mix of face-to-face and virtual interactions, providing a comprehensive learning environment (Garrison and Vaughan, 2008). Blended learning platforms can overcome geographic barriers, allowing fish farmers to access educational materials irrespective of their location. This adaptability is crucial in areas where physical attendance at training centres might be challenging (Katz, 2020). The use of online forums and interactive tools enhances engagement among learners. Collaborative projects and discussions facilitate knowledge sharing, which is essential for community-based fish farming practices (Nawaz, 2021). In the context of fish farming, blended learning can facilitate the teaching of

complex subjects such as fish biology, water quality management, and sustainable practices as platforms such as e-learning modules, webinars, and virtual simulations allow fish farmers to access training materials at their convenience. Studies indicate that online learning can enhance the understanding of technical concepts by providing interactive and multimedia resources (Zhang *et al.*, 2006). Also, traditional classroom settings enable hands-on experiences, essential for practical skills in fish farming. Workshops and field trips can complement online learning by allowing participants to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world environments (Huang and Liaw, 2012). The use of technologies such as mobile applications and data analytics tools in blended learning programs can further enhance fish farming practices and can aid in decision-making processes (Benson *et al.*, 2019). Recent studies have shown that blended learning can significantly improve educational outcomes in agricultural settings. The learning environments foster greater engagement and retention of knowledge among farmers compared to traditional learning methods (Gómez *et al.* (2018). Blended learning formats allow for greater flexibility and accessibility, enabling farmers to learn at their own pace as this increased accessibility helps accommodate the varying schedules of fish farmers, thereby encouraging participation (González *et al.* 2019). Blended learning can incorporate hands-on training sessions alongside online modules,

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providing a practical context for theoretical knowledge as this combination significantly improved the application of knowledge in real-world settings, leading to better farming practices (Kirkpatrick, 2016). Similarly, online forums and community interactions foster peer learning and knowledge sharing, which are essential in a field where farmers can greatly benefit from shared experiences; such interactions create a supportive learning environment that enhances knowledge retention and application (Bennett and Deal, 2015). Blended learning can reduce costs associated with traditional training methods as cost-effective training programs are crucial for small-scale fish farmers, who often operate with limited resources (Thompson and Waters, 2017). Traditional face-to-face training sessions often struggle to reach all farmers, particularly those in remote or rural areas. Miller and Smith (2018) emphasize that geographic barriers and limited transportation options hinder the participation of many fish farmers in training programs, which leads to uneven knowledge distribution and perpetuates existing disparities in aquaculture practices. Conventional training methods may not engage learners effectively. Gómez *et al.* (2018) found that passive learning environments often result in low retention rates, limiting the practical application of knowledge acquired. This is particularly concerning in a rapidly evolving field like fish farming, where staying updated on best practices is essential. While blended learning has the potential to

improve accessibility, the digital divide remains a significant barrier. González *et al.* (2019) highlight that many fish farmers lack access to reliable internet and digital literacy skills, which limits their ability to engage with online learning components effectively. This creates disparities between those who can benefit from blended learning and those who cannot. The adoption of new learning modalities may be met with skepticism among fish farmers accustomed to traditional methods. Nguyen *et al.* (2020) opined that cultural factors can influence farmers' willingness to participate in blended learning programs, affecting the overall effectiveness of such initiatives. However, despite its potential, the fish farming industry faces significant knowledge gaps among farmers regarding best practices, sustainability, and technological advancements. Traditional methods of information dissemination often prove inadequate in addressing these gaps, necessitating a more effective approach such as blended learning. This study explores the effectiveness of blended learning approaches in disseminating fish farming information in Kwara State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study describe the blended learning tools utilized in disseminating fish farming information, fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools, effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish farming information dissemination, benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming information, level of effectiveness of

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blended learning in fish farming information dissemination and constraints to effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination. It was hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information.

Methodology

This study was carried out in Kwara State Nigeria. Kwara is located within the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria and has its capital in Ilorin. State has total land area of 35,705Km². A multicultural and diverse population of 3,390,330 people (National Population Commission, 2006). Kwara State has 16 Local Government Areas (Kwara State Government Diary, 2025). It lies between latitudes 7°45'N and 9°30'N and longitudes 2°30'E and 6°25'E. The average temperature ranges between 27°C and 35°C with a mean annual rainfall of 1,000-1,500mm. It has two main seasons namely; wet and dry. The wet season is between early April and late October while the dry season is between November and late March. Crop farming is the mainstay of the economy of the state; the natural vegetation cover consists of rainforest in the South and Guinea Savannah to the North. The climatic condition, soil type, topography and vegetation cover in the state support the cultivation of several crops of economic importance like maize, cassava, vegetables, millet, rice, yam

cowpea and sorghum. The State is also suitable for raising livestock; it is positioned in the forested savannah and enjoys reasonable dry and wet seasons, with heavier rain falling in August and September (Kwara State Agricultural Development Project, 2014). The State is an inland water state naturally blessed with large volumes of water where fishermen provide food for an estimated population of about 168.8 million (World Bank 2012). Based on ecological characteristics, cultural practices and project administrative convenience, the state is categorized into four zones by Kwara State Agricultural Development Project (KWADP, 2014). These zones were labelled Zone A, B, C, and D and cover all 16 local government areas (LGAs) in the state. Zone A (Headquarters: Kaiama): Includes Baruteen and Kaima LGAs. Zone B (Headquarters: Patigi): Includes Edu and Patigi LGAs. Zone C (Headquarters: Malet/Shao): Includes Asa, Ilorin East, Ilorin South, Ilorin West, and Moro LGAs. Zone D (Headquarters: Igbaja): Includes Ekiti, Ifelodun, Offa, Oyun, Isin, and Oke-Ero LGAs. A multistage sampling procedure was employed for the selection of fish farmers for this study. Firstly, simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 3 zones namely Zone A, Zone C and Zone D. Secondly, 3 blocks was selected from each of the three agricultural development programme zones making a total of nine (9) blocks. The third stage involved a random selection of two (2) cells from each of the 9 blocks making a total of 18 cells. Lastly, a

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random selection of 10 fish farmers from each of the 18 cells making a total of one hundred and fifty (180) fish farmers that constituted the sample size for the study. Primary data was collected using a well-structured interview schedule. Data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools.

Results and Discussion

Blended learning tools utilized in disseminating fish farming information

As presented in Table 1, online platforms ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 1.98, mobile applications ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 1.95, traditional in-person methods ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 1.94 and social media ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 1.93 were the blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information in the study area. Blended learning combines various educational methods to enhance the dissemination of information in fish farming and each tool has distinct indications and implications for effective learning and knowledge transfer. This indicated that online platforms bring about increased accessibility to information for fish farmers, regardless of their geographical location as well as fostering a community of practice where users can share experiences and best practices. This implies that online platforms can provide comprehensive information on fish farming techniques, market trends, and environmental sustainability. They allow for the dissemination of multimedia content which cater to different

learning styles (Garrison and Kanuka, 2004). Mobile applications as a blended tool utilized for disseminating fish farming information indicated that it can provide real-time data on fish farming practices, weather updates, and market prices and facilitate on-the-go learning and support for farmers in remote areas. This implies that it enhances the ability to make informed decisions quickly, leading to better farming practices and increased productivity. It also encourages continuous learning and adaptation by providing instant access to updated information (Alvarez and Sanz, 2017). Similarly, utilizing traditional in-person methods as a blended tool for disseminating fish farming information indicated that it provide hands-on experience and direct interaction with experts which are particularly effective for demonstrating practical skills and techniques. This implies that it foster relationships and networks among farmers, leading to collaborative learning environments. Potentially higher engagement levels due to face-to-face interaction, which can lead to better retention of information (Bennett and Baird, 2010). Social media can be utilized for sharing success stories, tips, and expert advice on fish farming as they facilitate community engagement and peer support. This implies that rapid dissemination of information, enabling farmers to stay updated with the latest trends and practices and the potential for misinformation exists, necessitating critical evaluation of sources (Kumar and Gupta, 2017).

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Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by blended learning tools utilized in disseminating fish farming information (n=180)

Blended learning tools utilized in disseminating fish farming information	WMS	Rank
Traditional in-person methods	1.94	3 rd
Resource libraries	1.82	8 th
Community engagement tools	1.86	7 th
Social media	1.93	4 th
Multimedia resources	1.88	6 th
Online platforms	1.98	1 st
Mobile applications	1.95	2 nd
Interactive tools	1.91	5 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools

Table 2 revealed that the fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools were breeding techniques ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.05, water quality management ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 2.02, feeding and nutrition ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 1.99 and fish farming basics ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 1.97. Blended learning tools have proven effective for disseminating essential fish farming information as each of the information plays a critical role in successful fish farming practices and can benefit significantly from blended learning approaches. Breeding techniques as information disseminated through blended learning tools indicates that effective breeding techniques are

foundational for improving fish stock quality and yield which can be taught through both online tutorials and in-person workshops. This implies that understanding breeding techniques can lead to improved fish health and increased production as access to expert-led online resources can enhance farmer knowledge, while hands-on workshops solidify skills (Gjedrem, 2010). The finding indicates that water quality is crucial in fish farming, affecting fish health and growth. Online platforms can provide real-time monitoring tools and educational resources on parameters such as pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen levels. This implies that training farmers on water quality management through blended methods ensures that they can quickly address issues, thus minimizing losses and optimizing growth (Boyd and Tucker, 2012). Feeding and nutrition

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indicated that proper feeding techniques and nutritional knowledge increase fish growth rates and reduce feed costs thus online courses can offer insights into feed formulation and nutritional requirements. This implies that farmers equipped with knowledge about feeding can enhance feed efficiency and fish health, resulting in better economic returns (Tacon and Metian, 2013). Also, the dissemination of information on fish farming basics indicates

that a solid foundation in aquaculture principles is necessary for any fish farmer which can be introduced through interactive content and community engagement. This implies that by establishing a strong understanding of fish farming basics, farmers are better prepared to implement advanced techniques effectively, leading to sustainable practices and improved productivity (FAO, 2020).

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools (n=180)

Fish farming information disseminated through blended learning tools	WMS	Rank
Fish farming basics	1.97	4 th
Species selection	1.94	6 th
Water quality management	2.02	2 nd
Environmental sustainability	1.95	7 th
Regulations and compliance	1.78	13 th
Feeding and nutrition	1.99	3 rd
Health management	1.91	8 th
Economic and market information	1.88	9 th
Breeding techniques	2.05	1 st
Technological innovations	1.86	10 th
Business management	1.96	5 th
Community and networking	1.81	12 th
Research and development	1.84	11 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish farming information dissemination

Result presented in Table 3 revealed that the effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish

farming information dissemination in the study area were enhanced knowledge retention ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 1.88, improved access and knowledge dissemination ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 1.87,

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greater flexibility for farmers ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 1.85 and increased motivation and engagement ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 1.83. The utilization of blended learning tools effectively enhances the dissemination of fish farming information, resulting in numerous positive effects for fish farmers and each of these effects plays a crucial role in the overall effectiveness of blended learning approaches. This indicates that blended learning combines online resources with face-to-face instruction, which has been shown to improve knowledge retention rates and reinforce learning (Graham, 2013). This implies that higher retention rates can lead to better application of knowledge in practical settings, ultimately improving fish farming practices and productivity (Kearney, 2013). Also blended learning makes information more accessible, particularly for fish farmers in remote areas as online modules can be accessed at any time, allowing for ongoing learning (Kumar and Gupta, 2020). This implies that improved access can bridge the educational gap, ensuring that fish farmers have the necessary

information to make informed decisions (FAO, 2020). Similarly, the flexibility of blended learning allows fish farmers to learn at their own pace and schedule, accommodating their demanding routines (Graham, 2013). This implies that flexibility can lead to higher participation rates and lower dropout rates, as farmers can tailor their learning experiences to fit their needs (Kearney, 2013). Blended learning environments often incorporate various teaching methods which can engage learners more effectively than traditional methods (Graham, 2013). This implies that increased motivation and engagement can lead to a greater willingness to apply new knowledge and skills in fish farming practices, contributing to better outcomes (Tacon and Metian, 2013). The integration of these effects highlights the overall effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information. By enhancing knowledge retention, improving access, providing flexibility, and boosting engagement, blended learning approaches ensure that fish farmers are well-equipped with the necessary skills and information to succeed.

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish farming information dissemination (n=180)

Effects of utilizing blended learning tools for fish farming information dissemination	WMS	Rank
Enhanced knowledge retention	1.88	1 st
Improved practical skills	1.82	5 th
Increased motivation and engagement	1.83	4 th
Sustainability awareness	1.75	8 th

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Improved access and knowledge dissemination	1.87	2 nd
Increased productivity and income	1.80	6 th
Enhanced skill acquisition and management	1.73	9 th
Reduced mortality rates	1.77	7 th
Higher adoption rates of innovations	1.68	11 th
Greater flexibility for farmers	1.85	3 rd
Community building	1.71	10 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming information

Result in Table 4 shows that cost-effectiveness ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 2.02, access to up-to-date information ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 1.99, flexibility and accessibility ranked 3rd with a weighted mean score of 1.98 and improved skill acquisition ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 1.96 were the benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming information. Blended learning tools offer significant benefits in disseminating fish farming information, enhancing the effectiveness of educational initiatives. This indicates that blended learning reduces the overall costs associated with traditional training methods. This implies that cost-efficiency allows more fish farmers to participate in educational programs, increasing outreach and knowledge dissemination. Graham (2006) posited that blended learning can lead to substantial savings, enabling allocating of

resources effectively. The online component of blended learning provides immediate access to the latest research, practices, and trends in fish farming which implies that fish farmers are equipped with current knowledge, enhancing their decision-making capabilities. This is in tandem with the report of Allen and Seaman (2013) that online learning environments allow for real-time updates, ensuring relevant information is always available. Blended learning allows learners to access educational materials at their convenience, accommodating various schedules and learning paces. This flexibility can lead to higher engagement levels and completion rates. This is in agreement with the report of Garrison and Vaughan (2008) that flexible learning environments enhance learner satisfaction, making it more likely that fish farmers will pursue ongoing education. Likewise, blended learning combines theoretical knowledge with practical applications, facilitating better skill development as fish farmers can apply what they learn in real-world scenarios, leading to improved practices and

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productivity. This is in line with the report of Singh and Thurman (2019) that blended learning environments significantly enhance

skill acquisition in agricultural education, which can be directly applied to fish farming.

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming information (n=180)

Benefits of utilizing blended learning tools in disseminating fish farming Information	WMS	Rank
Empowerment and independence	1.95	5 th
Increased motivation	1.90	7 th
Assessment and feedback	1.82	11 th
Access to up-to-date information	1.99	2 nd
Improved knowledge retention	1.92	6 th
Cost-effectiveness	2.02	1 st
Enhanced engagement	1.88	8 th
Convenience	1.87	9 th
Improved skill acquisition	1.96	4 th
Real-time Interaction	1.85	10 th
Flexibility and accessibility	1.98	3 rd

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Level of effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination

Table 5 shows that the level of effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination is high as indicated by more than half of the respondents (58.3%) in the study area. Blended learning tools have shown a high level of effectiveness in disseminating fish farming information. Blended learning combines interactive online content with face-to-face instruction, which can significantly increase learner engagement and contribute to

better educational outcomes for fish farmers. This implies that engaged learners are more likely to retain information and apply it effectively in practice. This is in line with report of Baker (2004) that blended learning environments foster greater participation and retention, leading to improved outcomes in agricultural education. Also, the integration of varied instructional methods aids in better knowledge retention. This implies that fish farmers can apply learned information more effectively, translating theory into practice. This supports the report of Hattie (2009) that

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diverse instructional strategies enhance learning outcomes, especially in practical fields like fish farming. Similarly, blended learning provides access to a wide array of digital resources which allows fish farmers to access and explore a variety of perspectives and best practices. This is in line with the report of Allen and Seaman (2013) that the wealth of resources in online learning environments supports deeper understanding and innovation in practices. Learners can often tailor their educational experiences to fit their needs, choosing when and how to engage with materials. Customizability leads to higher satisfaction and effectiveness in learning, as

individuals can focus on areas where they need the most improvement. This supports the report of Garrison and Vaughan (2008) that personalized learning paths contribute to more effective educational outcomes. Blended learning can be disseminated to larger audiences without the constraints of physical space and resources. This scalability allows for widespread knowledge transfer, making it possible to educate more fish farmers efficiently. This is in tandem with the report of Graham (2006) that blended learning can effectively reach diverse populations, enhancing overall community knowledge.

Table 5: Distribution of the respondents by level of effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination

Level of effectiveness of blended learning	Frequency	Percentage
High	105	58.3
Moderate	65	36.1
Low	10	5.6
Total	180	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Constraints to effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination

Result presented in Table 6 revealed that constraints to effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination in the study area include digital divide ranked 1st with a weighted mean score of 1.68, technical skills and issues ranked 2nd with a weighted mean score of 1.65, resource limitations ranked 3rd

with a weighted mean score of 1.62 and engagement challenges ranked 4th with a weighted mean score of 1.58. Blended learning can significantly enhance the dissemination of fish farming information; however, its effectiveness is constrained by factors such as the digital divide, technical skill issues, resource limitations, and engagement challenges. This indicates that digital divide create gap between individuals who have access to digital

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technologies and those who do not. This implies that this divide can limit the reach of blended learning initiatives, particularly in rural or underserved areas where fish farming is prevalent. This is in tandem with the report of Warschauer (2003) that without equitable access to technology, educational programs may exacerbate existing inequalities rather than mitigate them. Also, technical skill issues indicate that many learners may lack the necessary technical skills to navigate blended learning platforms effectively. This implies that insufficient technical skills can lead to frustration and disengagement, reducing the overall effectiveness of the learning experience. This supports the report of Hew and Cheung (2014) that inadequate digital literacy can significantly impact learners' ability to benefit from online components, which are crucial for blended learning success. Limited access to

financial and material resources can restrict the implementation of effective blended learning programs. This implies that resource limitations can result in substandard educational materials and technology, impairing the learning experience. This is in line with the findings of Zhao *et al.* (2005) that resource limitations can lead to a lack of quality in educational offerings, which negatively affects learner outcomes. Engaging learners in a blended learning environment can be difficult, especially when transitioning from traditional classroom settings. This implies that low engagement levels can lead to high dropout rates and poor retention of information. This agrees with the findings of Garrison and Vaughan (2008) that without effective strategies to foster engagement, blended learning may fail to achieve its intended outcomes.

Table 6: Distribution of the respondents by constraints to effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information dissemination (n=180)

Constraints to effectiveness of blended learning in fish farming information Dissemination	WM S	Ran k
Digital divide	1.68	1 st
Content quality and relevance	1.55	5 th
Engagement challenges	1.58	4 th
Cultural factors	1.46	9 th
Sustainability of programmes	1.51	7 th
Resource limitations	1.62	3 rd
Regulatory and compliance issues	1.44	10 th
Instructor readiness	1.53	6 th

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Technical skills and issues	1.65	2 nd
Assessment and feedback challenges	1.49	8 th

WMS-Weighted mean score

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Hypothesis testing

There is no significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information

Relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information

Correlation analysis presented in Table 7 shows that there is a significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information ($r=0.579$; $p=0.000$) and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information. Hence the initial hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information is hereby rejected. The significant relationship between blended learning tools and the effectiveness of blended learning is characterized by a cycle of improved learning

experiences and outcomes. The effective use of these tools not only enhances knowledge acquisition but also encourages ongoing learning and adaptation among fish farmers thus underscoring the importance of integrating various educational methods to achieve optimal learning outcomes for fish farmers. The significant relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information ($r=0.579$; $p=0.000$) and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information indicates that blended learning approaches can lead to improved academic performance and knowledge retention as studies indicate that farmers often perform better when exposed to a mix of online and face-to-face learning experiences (Graham, 2013). This implies that for fish farmers, this means that the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical skills can significantly improve their understanding and application of fish farming practices (Kearney, 2013). Also, the significant relationship indicates that blended learning tools often incorporate interactive and multimedia elements that enhance engagement, motivate learners and make the learning process more enjoyable (Kumar and Gupta, 2020). This implies that increased engagement can lead to

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higher participation rates among fish farmers, making them more likely to adopt new techniques and improve their farming practices (Tacon and Metian, 2013). Blended learning allows learners to access information anytime and anywhere, which is particularly beneficial for fish farmers with varying schedules (Graham, 2013). This implies that this flexibility can lead to greater inclusivity, ensuring that more farmers can benefit from training and

resources, regardless of their location or time constraints (FAO, 2020). Likewise, blended learning can foster a sense of community among fish farmers, facilitating peer-to-peer support and knowledge sharing (Kearney, 2013). This implies that building a community can enhance the effectiveness of learning, as farmers can collaborate, share experiences, and solve problems together, leading to improved practices and outcomes (Gjedrem, 2010).

Table 7: Summary of correlation analysis showing the relationship between blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information and the effectiveness of blended learning in disseminating fish farming information

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision
Blended learning tools utilized for disseminating fish farming information	0.579	0.000	Significant

Significant at 5% level of significance

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Conclusion and recommendations

In conclusion, blended learning is a powerful approach for disseminating fish farming information, offering benefits such as enhanced engagement, accessibility to up-to-date resources, and improved skill acquisition. The effective combination of traditional teaching methods with digital tools has proven to facilitate better knowledge retention and application among fish farmers. While the high level of effectiveness of blended learning tools is evident, it is essential to address the constraints that limit their potential, particularly the digital divide and varying levels of technical skills among users. By overcoming these challenges,

the impact of blended learning in the fish farming sector can be further amplified, leading to sustainable practices and improved livelihoods for fish farmers. It was recommended that;

1. Implementation of training programs aimed at improving the digital literacy of fish farmers to ensure they can effectively utilize blended learning tools.
2. Addressing the digital divide by providing resources such as subsidized internet access, mobile learning devices, and community learning centres equipped with technology.

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3. Creating interactive and engaging educational materials that cater to different learning styles to enhance participation and retention.

4. Leveraging local agricultural experts and successful fish farmers to contribute to content development and delivery, making the learning experience more relatable and applicable.

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5. Continuous assessment of the effectiveness of blended learning initiatives through feedback from participants and adapts the programs based on their needs and challenges.

6. Building online and offline communities where fish farmers can share experiences, ask questions, and support one another, further enhancing the learning process.

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